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Abstract: Today, media culture plays a unique and important role in raising the morale of society. Media, information media and communication networks are used as the main means of implementing social, political, economic and cultural changes in society. It is possible to spread moral, aesthetic, cultural and social values among people with the help of media culture in raising spirituality. In this article, the role of media culture in raising the morale of the society is analyzed and opinions are presented.

Key words: Society, spirituality, culture, globalization, media literacy, information technology, Internet.

In cultural studies, media culture means the modern Western capitalist society that emerged and was formed under the influence of mass media and social networks in the 20th century[1:56]. In its place, this term refers to the general and intellectual influence of mass media not only on public opinion, but also on tastes and values, as well as on society.

Knowing the elements of social networks and mass culture is today's urgent task. We are currently living in the era of modern technology, we prefer the internet to various socio-political newspapers, books and TV shows when looking for any information we want, any information we need. The reason is that information on social networks, that is, on the Internet, is updated frequently. It does not cause any difficulties for us to use the Internet.

According to the European Union documents, media education is media competence, which should be understood as a critical and thoughtful attitude to the media in order to educate responsible citizens who are able to express their opinion based on the information received. development oriented education. This is the use of information necessary for citizens, its analysis, identification of economic, social and cultural interests related to them. Media culture is a set of knowledge, skills and abilities needed to analyze, evaluate, and create various media works.

Media culture is a necessary part of personal culture, familiarization with the types of mass media, the information distributed through them, theoretical knowledge, practical skills, acquisition of skills in the relevant fields based on their selection, sorting, analysis and evaluation. thorough acquisition, the sum of abilities to skillfully apply this knowledge in professional, everyday, cultural, spiritual and educational (practical) activities. In essence, the acquisition of

media culture by a person is not a spontaneous process, but is based on evolutionary development in several stages [2:109].

In the conditions of rapid development of information technologies, information security is of great importance in ensuring the national interests of the individual, society, and the state. It is known that material, socio-political interest lies at the bottom of every piece of information. But using information against national and international interests is a crime. Today, information is becoming the main and terrible weapon in the hands of some countries of the world and international terrorist organizations. The reason is that information reaches people's attention in the most convenient, fastest and most effective way.

The emergence of the Internet system is changing the consciousness and spiritual culture of mankind. The emergence of this system has many positive effects, such as information exchange between humanity and society, acceleration of economic relations, awareness of news in political and social spheres, facilitation of cultural and spiritual relations between institutions and millions of people. It is known to have created opportunities.

At the same time, it would not be wrong to say that the Internet system is changing the culture and spirituality of society in a negative way. Because the destructive forces trying to use the Internet for various nefarious purposes, the slanders, fabricated messages and videos being sent by them into this system have increased tremendously; it is also necessary to mention that the Internet has a negative effect on poisoning the human heart and mind, morals and psyche.

Therefore, if we people today first of all know what media culture is and its place in society, we will never get lost or be deceived.

Media culture is a culture formed under the influence of mass media. It provides a person's need for information, manages people's interests, attracts people, uses various forms of influence, methods and tools, and skills [3:138]. Today, media culture controls the mind and thinking of young people. Media culture has stuck to our society like weeds. There is no way to be a stranger to him. Now it is necessary to rationally manage the process of young people entering the media culture and connecting with it.

The concept of media culture is different from the concept of "mass culture". Media culture is a product of the globalization process. Therefore, just like globalization itself, it has both positive and negative aspects. It is necessary to accept and develop the positive side, be careful with the negative side, and protect ourselves from its unfortunate consequences. Today, the role of mass media in our country is increasing in every field. Mass media is an important tool for ensuring the openness of the activities of state authorities and administrative bodies, establishing public control over them. It acts as a strong bridge between the government and the people.

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Today's society's demand for information is higher than ever. This situation imposes a huge responsibility on media workers. In particular, the cross-cutting issue of problematic issues in different sections of the society increases the sense of trust in the mass media and makes them look at it as a support.

The role of media culture in raising the morale of society is very important. Through the media, information, values and cultures are conveyed to every layer of society. Therefore, media culture plays a major role in the spiritual development of society. Here are some suggestions and recommendations to ensure the role of media culture in raising the morale of society:

- ✚ Media education and promotion;
- ✚ Ensuring accuracy and reliability of information;
- ✚ Promotion of cultural heritage and national values;
- ✚ Using the media with a responsible approach;
- ✚ Educating young people through the media;
- ✚ Social advertising and promotions in mass media;
- ✚ Increasing attention of journalists to ethics and professionalism.

In this way, media culture is an important tool in raising the moral level of society, and every measure taken in this regard serves to improve society.

We can see the latest changes in this regard, as well as the example of extensive reforms being implemented in the system. The head of our state paid special attention to this issue in his holiday greetings to the employees of the sector. "Special importance is attached to strengthening the public relations of state agencies. In particular, the authorities and management bodies are constantly organizing press conferences, briefings, and open dialogues regarding the progress of reforms implemented in our country, the implementation of national programs and strategies.

Media culture has a great role in raising the morale of society. Moral, cultural and social values can be promoted through media, especially television, internet and social media. At the same time, it is necessary to develop a culture of information analysis in society in order to fight against the negative effects of media culture, to prevent false information and discrimination. Thus, by improving media culture, spreading positive information and avoiding negative consequences, great results can be achieved in raising the morale of society.

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